

Design and Development of Tube-Launched Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

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Abstract-Tube-Launched UAV with folding tandem wing configuration has great potential for military applications since there is an urgent need to have UAV that could be easily transported and deployed. This UAV was designed to have tandem wing configuration with approximately 50 ft in span and capable to be folded into 5 inch tubular pneumatic launcher.

When the UAV is launched from the tube, the wings will rapidly expand and the UAV will autonomously fly with a cruising speed of approximately 25 m/s. The airframe of the UAV was constructed by lightweight material such as carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP), aluminum, and plywood. This tube launched folding wing UAV was equipped with a camera as the payload for certain autonomous monitoring mission. The main focus of this paper is to present the general design process starting from design requirements, initial sizing, structural and aerodynamic analysis, folding mechanism, electrical system architecture, and pneumatic launcher design. Furthermore, a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation was conducted to predict the aerodynamic characteristics of the UAV. The results of the flight testing showed that the UAV was very stable and it achieved flight endurance of approximately 30 minutes. This paper presents the overall design process, analysis of UAV characteristics and the discussion of flight test data log.

Keywords: tube launched UAV, Folding Wing UAV, tandem wing UAV, compact UAV design

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) have wide purpose and can perform various missions such as monitoring, exploring, and military mission [1]. There are several challenges in UAV development and application including transporting and deploying the UAV. Most UAVs take too much space to be carried before it is launched and finishes the mission. It is also time consuming for user to assembly and launch the UAV [2][6]. Especially in military application, there is an urgent need of easily transported and deployed UAV.

Tube launched folding wing UAV is a concept that can solve the problem on easily transported and quickly launched UAV [3]. It provides the opportunity to launch UAV in difficult field and bring flexibility on launching the UAV instead of using specific launcher for specific field. The UAV is packed in a tube and then user can launch the UAV so the UAV come out from the tube [4]. The development of the tube launched folding wing UAV in this paper uses tandem wing configuration. This paper will also provide analysis of the UAV on stability, fluid dynamics, and also the performance of the UAV after several flight testings.

II. DESIGN REQUIREMENT & OBJECTIVES

TABLE I DESIGN REQUIREMENT AND OBJECTIVES

Specification	DRO
Type	Fixed Wing
Take off method	Hand Launch / Tube-Launch
Landing method	Belly Landing
Carrier / packaging	Able to put inside PVC pipe 6 inch
Flight mode	manual, Semi-auto, Fully Autonomous
Cruise speed	25 m/s
Operating altitude	60 - 200 m
Endurance time	up tp 30 minutes
MTOW	4 Kg
Wingspan	1.5 m

III. COMPARATIVE STUDY

Before determining the detailed configuration, it is necessary to look for comparison on other UAV. We chose 2 options that presented in table below.

TABLE II COMPARATIVE STUDY

Specification	Coyote	Switchblade
Weight (kg)	5.89	2.7
Wingspan (m)	1.47	0.6
Endurance (min)	120	15
Top Speed (m/s)	28.3	43.7
Launching	Canister Launched	Self Contained GroundLaunch
Image		

IV. WEIGHT ESTIMATION

The maximum take off weight (MTOW) of the UAV based on the DRO is 4 kg. The overall weight is classified into four main components including airframe, avionics, payload, and propulsion. The UAV airframe takes the highest portion of overall weight which consists of wing, spar, folding mechanism fuselage, tail, and other structures as shown in figure 1. The structural parts are produced using CFRP (wing), GFRP (fuselage and tail), aluminum (spar and folding mechanism), and high density foam to maintain the shape of the structural parts. The electronic system of the UAV includes battery, autopilot, servo, GPS, telemetry transmitter, video transmitter, and R/C receiver. Furthermore, the payload and propulsion used are respectively a camera and an electric motor.

Fig. 1 UAV Weight Distribution

V. INITIAL SIZING

The UAV must satisfy the requirements that it has to be able to be folded into a tubular package or launcher within a circular diameter of 6 in. This leads to a tandem wing with expandable wing UAV configuration as shown in figure 2. The tandem wing configuration can increase the lifting surface area (wings) whereas a compact design can be achieved by using folding wing configuration. By paying attention to the geometrical constraints and several design considerations, the initial sizing of the UAV prototype can be seen on Table IV.

Fig. 2 (a) Folded Condition (b) Transition Condition (c) Expanded Condition

TABLE III INITIAL SIZING

Definition	Value
Length L	1124 mm
Chord Length $c1$	100 mm
Chord Length $c2$	100 mm
Canard Span $b1$	1318 mm
Wing Span $b2$	1508 mm
Vertical Stabilizer h	300 mm
Canard-Wing LE distance d	635 mm
Canard-Wing Gap (Left) yL	75 mm
Canard-Wing Gap (Right) yR	75 mm
Left-Right Lifting Surfaces	11 mm
Vertical Gap y_s	
Distance between vertical stabilizers	118 mm
Canard Airfoil	NACA 8408
Wing Airfoil	NACA 8408
Vertical Stabilizer Airfoil	NACA 0010
MTOW	4 kg
Cruise Speed	25 m/s
Altitude	100 m

Fig. 3 UAV 3D Model

Fig. 4 Elevon Control System

VI. AERODYNAMICS ANALYSIS

A. Airfoil Selection

A low reynold number airfoils from NACA 4-series and Miley were chosen as candidate for sectional wing configuration.

Fig. 5 Airfoil Comparison

B. Stability Characteristic Prediction

In order to analyze the stability characteristic of the UAV, a simple estimation was conducted using XFLR5. It is free open source software, developed and distributed under General Public License, GNU [7]. It can provide a quick estimation of idealized aircraft model consisting wing, tail, and fuselage. In this study, a full configuration of UAV with simple model was defined to be analyzed in XFLR as shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6 XFLR Full Configuration

Fig. 7 Root Locus

Figure 7 represents both longitudinal and lateral stability in term of root locus diagram. The lateral stability has two symmetric dutch roll modes, one roll damping mode and one spiral mode. In addition, the longitudinal stability has two symmetric phugoid modes, and two symmetric short period modes[5]. Based on the presented root locus analysis, the UAV is characterized to be stable in both longitudinal and lateral mode.

C. CFD Analysis

The aerodynamic characteristics of the UAV was analyzed using high fidelity software : Ansys CFX. The Ansys CFX solver uses Reynold Averaging Navier-Stokes (RANS) for solving the numerical model.

The 3D geometry file was imported to ANSYS CFX Mesher to conduct the discretization of the model. In CFX-Pre, the boundary conditions are defined with its respective properties such as inlet, wall, opening, and outlet. After the simulation setup was done, the CFX solver started to solve the numerical model. Figure 8 and 9 show the CL vs. Angle of attack and the drag polar, respectively.

Fig. 8 CL vs Angle of Attack

Fig. 9 CL vs CD

VII. AVIONICS SYSTEM

The system is powered by LiPo battery 4S 6200 mAH. It uses autopilot board Pixhawk as flight controller. The propulsion uses brushless DC motor. The communication system uses 2 different frequency for flight data and remote control data from pilot command.

Fig. 10 Avionics System Architecture

The power distribution between autopilot and actuator is separated to prevent back EMF that can affect other component. With this configuration, the UAV can flight autonomous with certain Ground Control Station software in user PC.

VIII. DETAILED DESIGN

The following figures show the internal layout and the folding mechanism of the wing. The folding mechanism involves a torsional spring to deploy the wings. The mechanism is designed in such way that would enable the wing to be extended quickly using the force from the torsional spring [2].

Fig. 11 Internal Layout

Fig. 12 Folding Mechanism

IX. TESTING

Several flight tests had been successfully conducted in order to check and verify performance of the UAV. Some results of the flight test performance have also been recorded based on data flash log from UAV flight controller as shown in (Figure).

Fig. 13 Flight Test

Based on the flight tests data, we get several results of performance of the UAV as stated below.

- The maximum airspeed measured is 100 km/h
- Climb rate is up to 150 m / minutes
- Stall speed of the UAV approximately 45 km/h for 3 kg take-off weight
- Maximum relative altitude reach is about 160 meters.

Longest flight time is around 26 minutes nonstop in autonomous mode from battery level 16.7 Volts until 14.8 Volts.

and performed stable flight. The improvement can be focused on the launching mechanism and mission fulfillment

Fig. 14 Flight Test Data Log

Fig. 15 Flight Test Log Data : Navigation

The flight test came up with slight problem when fly on autonomous mode. The guidance is unstable. After analysis on data log, we found that the unconventional UAV configuration need improvement on a parameter at autopilot. This is because the UAV is so agile that the target bearing, a measurement to give UAV direction on autonomous mode and nav bearing, the actual bearing value is so distinct. The phenomenon is shown in **figure 15**. Authors solved the problem by reconfigure the value of navigation parameter.

We successfully improved the development of the UAV iteratively by overcoming several emerging problems such as lateral-directional stability of the UAV, attitude control tuning, and guidance path tuning in autonomous mission of the UAV by analyzing the flight test performance and data.

X. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on result and analysis data, entire DRO hav been achieved. The UAV also had been tested

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